

LOADS CONTAINER -PLATFORM AT A TRANSPORT TECHNICAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL RECOMMENDATIONS ON

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Annotation. *This in the article, recommendations are developed on the implementation of the transportation of grain cargoes that do not fit into universal containers on a container platform. In the system of intermodal transportation of grain cargo, a system of vehicles is used, which has certain parameters for transportation in open traffic, as well as relationships between the values of the parameters of the cargo, fastening means and the vehicle.*

Main part _ Today, it is proposed to use a container-platform for grain cargo transported as part of open traffic. However, to date, the implementation of the return of the container platform and reusable fasteners remains a pressing issue. Research is being carried out on the topic "Solving the problem of cargo transportation in the expanded nomenclature in intermodal transportation through the creation of an innovative container platform and a new technical and technological solution."

The design features of the container platform consist of combining two components of the intermodal transport system - the container itself and the means of fastening. A 3D model of a container-platform based on a 20-foot container was developed based on the studies conducted using SolidWorks software .

Figure 1. A view of the container platform

The study of stress-strain state problems was carried out using the finite element method .

Figure 2 . Container-platform body structure finite element model

Modeling during container platform _ of forces application _ and of the model deformed The situation is shown in Figure 3 .

Figure 3 . Container platform of energy in the elements distribution

The results of the stress-strain state analysis according to the specified conditions are shown in Figure 4 .

Container platform recommendation done option modeling as a result received results consistency in terms of the most acceptable construction to determine possibility gave

Loads either _ descriptive statistics in nomenclature container platform through transport possible has been of cargo code signs given.

The only definition of loads is statistical nomenclature loads _ own _ into takes , railway transport through transport documents in preparation used code signs is considered

Loads either _ descriptive statistics nomenclature of cargo code the following
The information is : _

1. Definition groups according to goods list, position of goods positions and numbers given.

2. Cargo alphabet in the order gi list _ given.

Cargo code six ra q amdan consists of and the following to structure has:

- the first two number – load definition group;
- the third number – definition of the cargo object in the group number;
- the fourth and fifth numbers – definition position load series number;
- the sixth number – technical, economic and social data of classifiers codes protection to do for control numbers count and to apply methodology according to calculated control number _

There are many factors that go into making the shipping process efficient. These include choosing the right mode of transport, choosing an efficient means of transport, choosing the transport unit and type of shipment, choosing the right mode of transport, etc. enters _

A container-platform is an intermodal transport unit. Cargo that does not require weather protection is transported on the container platform by rail, road, water transport. The cargo accepted for transportation is carried out in cases where it is not possible to transport it in other types of universal ISO containers according to their dimensions. For transportation on container platforms, grain cargo such as wood, reinforced concrete products, metal structures, heavy loads, wheeled and tracked machines and industrial equipment are allowed.

One of the important factors is the effective use of loading and unloading mechanisms, the correct organization of the transportation process, and ensuring the safe delivery of goods. In order to ensure traffic safety, it is necessary to use the right selection of means of placing and fixing loads in open traffic structures.

Conclusion: The most optimal transportation of goods in Transopt is to transport goods to their destination with low cost, to deliver them without delay, and

to deliver high-quality goods with safety. In this article, recommendations are developed for the wide use of container-platforms in the organization of efficient transportation of cargo in several modes of transport.

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